

As on 23-01-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended to add records in GC Institute table in the knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several GeneBank records of the crops in their databases. Example of Genebanks; AVGRIS (<http://seed.worldveg.org/>), ICRISAT (<http://genebank.icrisat.org/>) and USDA GRIN (<https://npgsweb.ars-grin.gov/gringlobal/search.aspx>)
2. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.
3. Data may also available in research articles.
4. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. There are four fields to be entered, three of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

1.2 GC Institute (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the name of the institute which is working on the germplasm preservation of a particular crop.
- Ensure there is **NO** previous record which has used the same crop and Institute to be created

1.3 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop germplasm itself.

1.4 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID